

A supplement to the report:

Nutrient value of Icelandic seafood – Labelling and provision of information

A report to Fisheries Iceland 2017

Key information and data tables in English

Ólafur Reykdal

Svanhildur Hauksdóttir

Natasa Desnica

Ingibjörg Þorvaldsdóttir

Arnljótur Bjarki Bergsson

Advisory report no. 05-17 October 2017
Supplement

ISSN 1670-7192

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4590901

A supplement to the report:

Nutrient value of Icelandic seafood – Labelling and provision of information

A report to Fisheries Iceland 2017

Key information and data tables in English

[Næringargildi sjávarafurða – Merkingar og svörun

Skýrsla til Samtaka fyrirtækja í sjávarútvegi]

October 2017

Ólafur Reykdal
Svanhildur Hauksdóttir
Natasa Desnica
Ingibjörg Þorvaldsdóttir
Arnljótur Bjarki Bergsson

Written for and sponsored by:

**Samtök fyrirtækja
í sjávarútvegi**

Report summary

<i>Titill / Title</i>	Næringargildi sjávarafurða – Merkingar og svörun – Viðauki á ensku / Nutrient value of seafood – Labelling and provision of information – Supplement in English		
<i>Höfundar / Authors</i>	Ólafur Reykdal, Svanhildur Hauksdóttir, Natasa Desnica, Ingibjörg Porvaldsdóttir, Arnljótur Bjarki Bergsson		
<i>Skýrsla / Report no.</i>	05-17	<i>Útgáfudagur / Date:</i>	Október 2017
<i>Verknr. / Project no.</i>	2002-2438		
<i>Styrktaraðilar /Funding:</i>	Samtök fyrirtækja í sjávarútvegi /Fisheries Iceland		
<i>Ágríp á íslensku:</i>	Markmið verkefnisins var að afla gagna um næringargildi íslenskra sjávarafurða til að hægt væri að bregðast við vaxandi þörf fyrir upplýsingagjöf á þessu sviði. Mælingar voru gerðar á próteini, fitu, vatni, ösku, steinefnum, fosfati og fitusýrum í 85 sýnum af sjávarafurðum. Sýni voru dæmigerð fyrir söluvörur íslensks sjávarútvegs sem voru tilbúnar til sendingar á markað. Sýnin voru stór til að draga úr áhrifum einstaklingsbreytileika. Um var að ræða fersk eða frosin flök bolfisks og flatfisks ásamt rækju, humar og loðnu (alls 16 tegundir fiska og krabbadýra). – Þessi viðauki inniheldur sömu gögn og aðalskýrslan en allar töflur eru með enskum texta og hluti meginmáls hefur verið þýddur á ensku.		
<i>Lykilorð á íslensku:</i>	<i>Sjávarafurðir Næringargildi Merkingar Upplýsingagjöf</i>		
<i>Summary in English:</i>	The purpose was to provide data on the nutrient value of Icelandic seafood to make it possible to respond to increasing number of inquiries regarding this topic. Protein, fat, water, ash, minerals, phosphates, and fatty acids were analysed in 85 seafood samples. Samples were typical for the products from Icelandic seafood industries ready. Big samples were collected to reduce the effects of individual variation. Samples were fresh or frozen fillets of groundfish and additionally prawn, lobster and capelin (altogether 16 species). – This supplement includes the same data as the main report but tables have English explanations and a part of the main text has been translated to English.		
<i>English keywords:</i>	<i>Seafood Nutrient declaration Labelling Information provision</i>		

Content

1 Introduction	5
2. Materials and methods	6
2.1 Sampling.....	6
2.2 Analytical methods.....	7
3. Results	9
3.1 Proximates	9
3.2 Minerals	13
3.3 Fatty acids	17
3.4 Vitamins and trace elements	23
4. Provision of food information	24
5. References	28
6. Acknowledgement	29
Appendix 1 – Information for all seafood samples	30
Appendix 2 – Results for proximates in all seafood samples. Content per 100 g edible portion.	34
Appendix 3 – Results for minerals in all seafood samples. Content per 100 g edible portion.....	38
Appendix 4 – A sampling template	42
Appendix 5 – A registration template for sample information	43

1 Introduction

Results from the project *Nutrient value of Icelandic seafood – Labelling and provision of information* (is. Næringargildi sjávarafurða – merkingar og svörun) are reported. The project was funded by Fisheries Iceland and carried out by Matis – Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D. Work on the project started in September 2016 and sampling was carried out for one year. Results were reported in October 2017.

Careful sampling was emphasized. Samples contained at least 10 individual fishes. Samples were typical for the products exported from Icelandic fisheries. A total of 85 samples were analysed. The following components were analysed: Protein, fat, water, ash, minerals (sodium, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium), total phosphates and fatty acids.

Data tables are provided in this supplement together with key information.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sampling

Requirements for samples were as follows:

- Groundfish, general, minimum 10 fishes or fillets
- Small fishes (e.g. herring and mackerel), minimum 20 fishes
- Capelin, minimum 12 kg frozen block
- Prawn, minimum 1 kg or 2 packages
- Lobster, minimum 50 tails.

Table 1 lists the species investigated and Table 2 lists further information on samples.

Table 1. Species investigated in the project.

Icelandic name	English name	Latin name
Djúpkarfi	Deepwater redfish	<i>Sebastes mentella</i> (Travin, 1951)
Hlýri	Spotted catfish	<i>Anarhichas minor</i> Olafsen, 1772
Humar	Lobster	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Keila	Tusk, torsk, cusk	<i>Brosme brosme</i> (Ascanius, 1772)
Kolmunni	Blue whiting	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> (Risso, 1827)
Langa	Ling	<i>Molva molva</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Langlúra	Witch, pole dab	<i>Glyptocephalus cynoglossus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Loðna	Capelin	<i>Mallotus villosus</i> (Müller, 1776)
Makríll	Atlantic mackerel	<i>Scomber scombrus</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Rækja	Prawn, shrimp	<i>Pandalus borealis</i> Krøyer, 1838
Rækja	Prawn, shrimp	<i>Pandalus jordani</i> Rathbun, 1902
Rækja	Prawn, shrimp	<i>Pandalus montagui</i> Leach, 1814
Síld	Atlantic herring	<i>Clupea harengus</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Steinbítur	Wolf-fish, catfish	<i>Anarhichas lupus</i> Linnaeus, 1758
Stórkjafta	Megrim	<i>Lepidorhombus whiffiagonis</i> (Walbaum, 1792)
Ufsi	Pollock, saithe	<i>Pollachius virens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Ýsa	Haddock	<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Þorskur	Atlantic cod	<i>Gadus morhua</i> Linnaeus, 1758

Table 2. Sample types and number of samples.

Sample	Condition	Number
Blue whiting, fillet	Frozen	3
Blue whiting, headed and gutted	Frozen	3
Capelin, whole, male fish	Frozen	3
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	Frozen	3
Cod flesh, mince	Frozen	3
Cod skin	Fresh	3
Cod, fillet	Frozen, fresh	3
Cod, fillet / pieces, light salted	Frozen	10
Deepwater redfish, fillet	Frozen	2
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	Frozen	3
Ling, fillet	Frozen	3
Ling, fillet, light salted	Frozen	1
Lobster, tail	Frozen	3
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	Frozen	5
Megrim, fillet	Frozen	1
Pole dab, fillet	Frozen, fresh	3
Pollock, fillet, light salted	Frozen	1
Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , cooked and peeled	Frozen	12
Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , cooked and peeled	Frozen	1
Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , cooked and peeled	Frozen	3
Salted fish, ling, split	Refrigerated	1
Salted fish, pollock, split	Refrigerated	1
Spotted catfish, fillet	Frozen, fresh	4
Tusk, torsk, cusk	Frozen	3
Wolf-fish, fillet	Frozen, fresh	7
Total number of samples		85

2.2 Analytical methods

Protein

The method of Kjeldahl (ISO 2005) was used to determine protein. The factor used to convert nitrogen to protein was 6.25, except for cod skin where factor of 5.55 was used.

Fat

Fat was determined by the method of Bligh and Dyer (1959) with modification according to Hanson and Olley (1963).

Ash

Ash was determined after heating in a furnace at 550°C according to ISO method 5984 (ISO 2002).

Water

Water was determined by drying at 103 ± 2 °C for 4 hours (ISO 1999).

Minerals

Preparation of samples for mineral analysis was according to Sloth (Sloth o.fl. 2005) and measurements according to NMKL No 186-2007 (NMKL 2007), using an Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS). The instrument was from Agilent, Type 7500ce (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). Reference materials were analysed as can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Analytical results for a reference material (NMIJ CRM 7405-a, Hijiki) compared to certified values.

	Certified g/kg	Analysed g/kg
Sodium	16,2±0,2	13,1±2,6
Potassium	47,5±0,7	39,6±7,9
Magnesium	6,79±0,1	5,6±1,1
calcium	15,2±0,3	12,9±2,6
Phosphorus	1,01±0,03	0,9±0,2

Total phosphates

The method is based on the reaction of orthophosphate in an acid solution with ammonium molybdate and ammonium vanadate. Colorimetric measurements were carried out at 420 nm. The method is according to AOAC no. 963.31 (AOAC 1990).

Fatty acids

The analysis started with the isolation of fat by the Bligh and Dyer method. See information on fat analysis. Methylation was according to AOCS method Ce1b-89 (97) (AOCS 1997). For the detection of fatty acids, a Varian 3900 GC with 100 m column (fused silica capillary column, Omega Wax™ 250, 30 m × 25 mm × 25 mm µm film) and a flame ionisation detector, was used. The procedure was according to AOAC 996.06 (AOAC 2005).

Iodine

Measurements of iodine were carried out at LUFA-ITL GmbH in Kiel, Germany, by use of ICP-MS DIN 38406, E29 (NW).

Vitamin D

Measurements of vitamin D were carried out at LUFA-ITL GmbH in Kiel, Germany, by use HPLC-method (HPLC-VDLUFA Bd. III Kap. 13.8.1).

3. Results

3.1 Proximates

See Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Analytical results for proximates in seafood. Average $\pm$ standard deviation (min-max). Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
Groundfish						
Deepwater redfish, fillet	2	17,6 (16,9-18,2)	3,3 (2,4-4,2)	1,2 (1,1-1,2)	78,6 (78,2-79,0)	100,6 (100,5-100,7)
Spotted catfish, fillet	4	15,0 $\pm$ 1,1 (13,7-16,2)	3,4 $\pm$ 1,5 (2,0-4,7)	1,0 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,9-1,1)	81,5 $\pm$ 2,4 (78,4-83,5)	100,9 $\pm$ 0,7 (100,2-101,9)
Tusk, fillet	3	18,8 $\pm$ 0,9 (17,8-19,6)	0,5 $\pm$ 0,2 (0,2-0,6)	1,2 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,1-1,2)	80,1 $\pm$ 0,3 (79,8-80,3)	100,5 $\pm$ 0,9 (99,4-101,1)
Ling, fillet	3	19,6 $\pm$ 1,2 (18,3-20,7)	0,6 (0,6-0,6)	1,1 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,0-1,2)	79,0 $\pm$ 0,5 (78,6-79,6)	101,2 $\pm$ 0,2 (101,1-101,4)
Witch, fillet	3	17,1 $\pm$ 0,1 (17,0-17,2)	0,5 $\pm$ 0,04 (0,5-0,6)	1,1 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,1-1,2)	81,8 $\pm$ 0,5 (81,2-82,1)	100,5 $\pm$ 0,5 (99,9-100,9)
Wolf-fish, fillet	6	18,1 $\pm$ 1,5 (15,8-20,1)	1,0 $\pm$ 0,5 (0,4-1,8)	1,2 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,1-1,3)	81,0 $\pm$ 1,8 (78,4-83,5)	100,8 $\pm$ 0,6 (99,8-101,6)
Megrim, fillet	1	18,8	0,68	1,2	79,6	100,3
Cod, fillet	3	17,2 $\pm$ 0,2 (17,1-17,5)	0,7 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,6-0,8)	1,2 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,1-1,2)	82,0 $\pm$ 0,5 (81,5-82,5)	101,0 $\pm$ 0,2 (100,9-101,3)
Pelagic						
Blue whiting, fillet	3	19,0 $\pm$ 0,6 (18,3-19,4)	0,6 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,4-0,7)	1,7 $\pm$ 0,3 (1,4-2,0)	79,6 $\pm$ 0,9 (78,8-80,5)	100,9 $\pm$ 0,8 (100,0-101,6)
Blue whiting, headed	3	18,3 $\pm$ 0,2 (18,1-18,4)	0,8 $\pm$ 0,2 (0,5-1,0)	2,3 $\pm$ 0,4 (1,8-2,6)	78,6 $\pm$ 0,1 (78,5-78,7)	100,0 $\pm$ 0,5 (99,4-100,3)
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	3	14,7 $\pm$ 0,4 (14,2-15,0)	11,1 $\pm$ 0,5 (10,8-11,7)	1,9 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,8-1,9)	71,6 $\pm$ 1,4 (70,0-72,5)	99,2 $\pm$ 0,9 (98,3-100)
Capelin, whole, male fish	3	14,1 $\pm$ 0,4 (13,8-14,5)	9,9 $\pm$ 0,6 (9,3-10,5)	2,0 $\pm$ 0,3 (1,7-2,3)	73,6 $\pm$ 0,6 (73,0-74,2)	99,7 $\pm$ 0,5 (99,3-100,3)
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	5	16,8 $\pm$ 0,8 (15,8-17,8)	22,4 $\pm$ 3,5 (18,1-26,1)	1,2 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,1-1,3)	57,6 $\pm$ 3,7 (54,4-63,4)	98,0 $\pm$ 1,5 (96,8-100,6)
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	3	17,7 $\pm$ 0,5 (17,2-18,2)	10,7 $\pm$ 1,1 (9,5-11,7)	1,6 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,5-1,6)	69,6 $\pm$ 1,2 (68,2-70,3)	99,5 $\pm$ 0,3 (99,2-99,7)
Crustacean						
Lobster, tail	3	16,5 $\pm$ 0,7 (16,0-17,3)	0,7 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,6-0,8)	2,0 $\pm$ 0,1 (1,9-2,1)	80,9 $\pm$ 0,7 (80,4-81,7)	100,1 $\pm$ 0,5 (99,4-100,4)
Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , cooked	12	15,3 $\pm$ 1,3 (13,8-18,7)	1,0 $\pm$ 0,2 (0,6-1,3)	2,0 $\pm$ 0,2 (1,8-2,5)	82,4 $\pm$ 1,2 (79,6-84,0)	100,7 $\pm$ 0,5 (99,9-101,5)
Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , cooked	1	12,4	0,40	2,1	84,5	99,4
Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , cooked	3	15,4 $\pm$ 1,1 (14,3-16,5)	1,0 (1,0-1,1)	1,9 $\pm$ 0,3 (1,7-2,2)	82,1 $\pm$ 1,0 (81,3-83,2)	100,7 $\pm$ 0,6 (100,3-101,1)

Table 4 cont. Analytical results for proximates in seafood. Average $\pm$ standard deviation (min-max). Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
Light salted products						
Ling, fillet, light salted	1	15,7	0,55	2,7	82,2	101,2
Wolf-fish, fillet, little salted	1	14,6	1,39	1,3	83,5	100,8
Pollock, fillet, light salted	1	13,7	0,84	2,1	83,8	100,4
Cod, fillet, light salted	10	13,2 $\pm$ 1,4 (11,9-16,6)	0,5 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,3-0,7)	2,5 $\pm$ 0,4 (2,0-3,3)	84,4 $\pm$ 1,3 (81,1-85,6)	100,6 $\pm$ 0,3 (100,2-101,2)
Salted fish						
Salted fish, ling, split	1	25,2	0,90	20,0	60,9	107,0
Salted fish, pollock, split	1	24,2	1,54	19,1	55,8	100,6
Other products						
Cod skin	3	22,8 $\pm$ 0,4 (22,4-23,1)	0,4 $\pm$ 0,1 (0,3-0,5)	2,8 $\pm$ 0,3 (2,6-3,2)	73,9 $\pm$ 0,7 (73,1-74,4)	99,9 $\pm$ 0,7 (99,1-100,3)
Cod flesh, mince	3	15,9 $\pm$ 1,1 (14,7-16,7)	0,6 $\pm$ 0,2 (0,4-0,8)	1,1 $\pm$ 0,2 (1,0-1,3)	82,6 $\pm$ 1,4 (81,6-84,2)	100,2 $\pm$ 0,7 (99,5-101,0)

Table 5. Results for energy value of seafoods based on average composition, per 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Energy		Protein g	Fat g
		kJ	kcal		
Groundfish					
Deepwater redfish, fillet	2	421	100	17,6	3,31
Spotted catfish, fillet	4	382	91	15,0	3,44
Tusk, fillet	3	336	79	18,8	0,46
Ling, fillet	3	354	84	19,6	0,57
Witch, fillet	3	310	73	17,1	0,54
Wolf-fish, fillet	6	344	81	18,1	1,00
Megrim, fillet	1	345	81	18,8	0,68
Cod, fillet	3	317	75	17,2	0,65
Pelagic					
Blue whiting, fillet	3	345	81	19,0	0,59
Blue whiting, headed	3	341	80	18,3	0,81
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	3	660	159	14,7	11,09
Capelin, whole, male fish	3	605	145	14,1	9,86
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	5	1114	269	16,8	22,36
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	3	695	167	17,7	10,65
Crustacean					
Lobster, tail	3	306	72	16,5	0,69
Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , cooked and peeled	12	296	70	15,3	0,96
Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , cooked and peeled	1	226	53	12,4	0,40
Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , cooked and peel.	3	300	71	15,4	1,03
Light salted products					
Ling, fillet, light salted	1	287	68	15,7	0,55
Wolf-fish, fillet, little salted	1	300	71	14,6	1,39
Pollock, fillet, light salted	1	264	62	13,7	0,84
Cod, fillet, light salted	10	243	57	13,2	0,51
Salted fish					
Salted fish, ling, split	1	462	109	25,2	0,90
Salted fish, pollock, split	1	468	111	24,2	1,54
Other products					
Cod skin	3	402	95	22,8	0,41
Cod flesh, mince	3	293	69	15,9	0,60

3.2 Minerals

See Tables 6 and 7.

Table 6. Analytical results for minerals in seafood. Average $\pm$ standard deviation (min-max). Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Salt g	Sodium mg	Potassium mg	Magnesium mg	Calcium mg
Groundfish						
Deepwater redfish, fillet	2	0,21 (0,17-0,25)	84 (69-98)	300 (280-319)	34 (32-36)	28 (23-33)
Spotted catfish, fillet	4	0,21 $\pm$ 0,05 (0,15-0,27)	84 $\pm$ 21 (59-108)	313 $\pm$ 92 (199-417)	19 $\pm$ 5 (13-24)	7,3 $\pm$ 2,9 (3,0-9,0)
Tusk, fillet	3	0,22 $\pm$ 0,05 (0,16-0,27)	88 $\pm$ 21 (65-106)	233 $\pm$ 101 (119-310)	22 $\pm$ 0 (22-22)	14 $\pm$ 3,8 (10-17)
Ling, fillet	3	0,15 $\pm$ 0,02 (0,13-0,18)	60 $\pm$ 9 (52-70)	296 $\pm$ 36 (261-332)	22 $\pm$ 1 (22-23)	11 $\pm$ 7,5 (7,0-20)
Witch, fillet	3	0,26 $\pm$ 0,02 (0,24-0,28)	103 $\pm$ 9 (94-112)	222 $\pm$ 94 (124-312)	22 $\pm$ 1 (22-23)	22 $\pm$ 20 (6,0-44)
Wolf-fish, fillet	6	0,15 $\pm$ 0,03 (0,12-0,20)	58 $\pm$ 12 (48-81)	313 $\pm$ 46 (268-384)	21 $\pm$ 5 (18-30)	11 $\pm$ 4,0 (5,0-17)
Megrim, fillet	1	0,31	124	140	30	11,0
Cod, fillet	3	0,13 $\pm$ 0,01 (0,13-0,14)	52 $\pm$ 3 (50-56)	343 $\pm$ 68 (298-421)	20 $\pm$ 1 (19-20)	6,7 $\pm$ 4,6 (4,0-12)
Pelagic						
Blue whiting, fillet	3	0,49 $\pm$ 0,20 (0,31-0,70)	197 $\pm$ 79 (123-280)	311 $\pm$ 51 (274-369)	39 $\pm$ 13 (28-53)	39 $\pm$ 23 (13-56)
Blue whiting, headed	3	0,55 $\pm$ 0,21 (0,34-0,76)	222 $\pm$ 83 (137-302)	292 $\pm$ 23 (270-316)	44 $\pm$ 14 (31-59)	244 $\pm$ 197 (47-441)
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	3	0,42 $\pm$ 0,02 (0,41-0,44)	167 $\pm$ 8 (162-177)	231 $\pm$ 12 (217-240)	29 $\pm$ 3 (27-32)	173 $\pm$ 35 (132-195)
Capelin, whole, male fish	3	0,51 $\pm$ 0,12 (0,38-0,62)	204 $\pm$ 47 (153-246)	244 $\pm$ 4 (241-249)	38 $\pm$ 9 (28-44)	275 $\pm$ 48 (221-312)
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	5	0,26 $\pm$ 0,08 (0,16-0,35)	105 $\pm$ 31 (62-139)	342 $\pm$ 41 (302-410)	36 $\pm$ 15 (23-55)	19 $\pm$ 17 (5-44)
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	3	0,54 $\pm$ 0,05 (0,49-0,59)	217 $\pm$ 21 (195-237)	234 $\pm$ 70 (153-281)	44 $\pm$ 4 (40-47)	38 $\pm$ 22 (16-60)
Crustacean						
Lobster, tail	3	0,96 $\pm$ 0,05 (0,90-0,99)	382 $\pm$ 20 (360-396)	166 $\pm$ 91 (68-249)	53 $\pm$ 5 (48-58)	75 $\pm$ 32 (43-107)
Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , cooked	12	1,29 $\pm$ 0,24 (1,00-1,71)	517 $\pm$ 97 (398-682)	55 $\pm$ 28 (23-121)	20 $\pm$ 8 (11-40)	43 $\pm$ 17 (22-77)
Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , cooked	1	1,04	417	20	15	44,0
Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , cooked	3	1,29 $\pm$ 0,16 (1,13-1,44)	515 $\pm$ 63 (450-575)	66 $\pm$ 37 (40-109)	24 $\pm$ 7 (16-30)	36 $\pm$ 7,8 (27-41)

Table 6 cont. Analytical results for minerals in seafood. Average $\pm$ standard deviation (min-max). Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Salt g	Sodium mg	Potassium mg	Magnesium mg	Calcium mg
Light salted products						
Ling, fillet, light salted	1	1,98	790	63	17	8,0
Wolf-fish, fillet, little salted	1	0,69	274	158	13	5,0
Pollock, fillet, light salted	1	1,24	494	218	18	12,0
Cod, fillet, light salted	10	1,60 $\pm$ 0,35 (1,22-2,20)	642 $\pm$ 138 (487-880)	167 $\pm$ 65 (52-262)	17 $\pm$ 11 (10-48)	16 $\pm$ 20 (2-65)
Salted fish						
Salted fish, ling, split	1	16,00	6401	200	29	42,0
Salted fish, pollock, split	1	22,08	8833	332	47	43,0
Other products						
Cod skin	3	0,26 $\pm$ 0,22 (0,10-0,51)	105 $\pm$ 86 (38-202)	115 $\pm$ 59 (63-179)	20 $\pm$ 14 (7-34)	450 $\pm$ 322 (96-726)
Cod flesh, mince	3	0,39 $\pm$ 0,24 (0,19-0,66)	157 $\pm$ 97 (77-264)	238 $\pm$ 80 (151-307)	25 $\pm$ 11 (13-34)	8,3 $\pm$ 0,6 (8,0-9,0)

Table 7. Analytical results for phosphorus and total phosphates in seafood. Average $\pm$ standard deviation (min-max). Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Number of samples	Phosphorus mg	Total phosphates mg
Groundfish			
Deepwater redfish, fillet	2	172 (163-180)	
Spotted catfish, fillet	4	187 $\pm$ 46 (144-252)	
Tusk, fillet	3	134 $\pm$ 29 (101-157)	
Ling, fillet	3	158 $\pm$ 11 (146-166)	
Witch, fillet	3	124 $\pm$ 25 (96-145)	
Wolf-fish, fillet	6	178 $\pm$ 15 (163-201)	
Megrim, fillet	1	117	
Cod, fillet	3	176 $\pm$ 9 (170-187)	476 $\pm$ 18 (461-496)
Pelagic			
Blue whiting, fillet	3	185 $\pm$ 18 (165-201)	
Blue whiting, headed	3	295 $\pm$ 100 (183-375)	
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	3	294 $\pm$ 61 (237-359)	
Capelin, whole, male fish	3	318 $\pm$ 51 (279-376)	
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	5	208 $\pm$ 12 (189-220)	
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	3	217 $\pm$ 52 (158-257)	491 $\pm$ 18 (475-510)
Crustacean			
Lobster, tail	3	174 $\pm$ 28 (142-191)	
Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , cooked	12	96 $\pm$ 31 (56-148)	232 $\pm$ 72 (146-351)
Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , cooked	1	75	259
Prawn, <i>P. montequi</i> , cooked	3	101 $\pm$ 39 (78-146)	263 (193-333)
Light salted products			
Ling, fillet, light salted	1	75	223
Wolf-fish, fillet, little salted	1	111	292
Pollock, fillet, light salted	1	128	314
Cod, fillet, light salted	10	117 $\pm$ 36 (60-187)	305 $\pm$ 88 (219-484)
Salted fish			
Salted fish, ling, split	1	135	299
Salted fish, pollock, split	1	240	404
Other products			
Cod skin	3	343 $\pm$ 183 (135-477)	
Cod flesh, mince	3	139 $\pm$ 42 (92-174)	

3.3 Fatty acids

See Tables 8 to 11.

Table 8. Fatty acids in seafoods. %fatty acid methyl esters. Fat as g/100g.

No	Sample	Fat g/100g	Saturates	Monoun- saturates	Polyun- saturates	Polyunsat. n6	Polyunsat. n3	Polyunsat. other	Polyunsat. n3 long	Unknown fatty acids	Sum
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	11,7	22,8	49,4	24,3	1,6	20,8	1,9	18,5	3,5	100,0
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	17,2	22,2	53,4	19,9	1,6	17,3	1,1	14,5	4,4	100,0
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	17,8	21,5	54,9	18,7	1,4	16,3	1,0	13,6	5,0	100,0
	Average	15,6	22,2	52,6	21,0	1,5	18,1	1,3	15,5	4,3	100,0
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	10,8	20,4	52,4	23,7	1,6	20,9	1,2	19,0	3,5	100,0
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	11,7	20,3	50,0	26,7	2,1	23,5	1,1	21,5	3,0	100,0
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	10,8	19,9	52,8	25,1	2,2	21,6	1,2	19,6	2,3	100,0
	Average	11,1	20,2	51,7	25,1	2,0	22,0	1,2	20,0	2,9	100,0
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	18,1	23,6	36,9	35,3	2,7	29,2	3,5	22,3	4,1	100,0
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	19,6	24,4	34,5	37,5	2,7	33,3	1,5	25,2	3,6	100,0
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	26,1	22,1	41,0	32,8	2,4	29,4	1,0	23,1	4,2	100,0
	Average	21,3	23,4	37,5	35,2	2,6	30,6	2,0	23,5	4,3	100,0
47	Lobster, tail	0,6	22,1	22,3	53,2	3,4	35,7	14,1	35,2	2,4	100,0

Table 9. Saturated fatty acids in seafoods. %fatty acid methyl esters.

No.	Sample	C12:0	C14:0	C15:0	C16:0	C17:0	C18:0	C20:0	C23:0	Sum
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	7,0	0,4	13,8	0,2	1,1		0,2	22,8
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	7,6	0,4	12,8	0,1	1,0	0,2		22,2
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	7,6	0,4	12,1	0,1	1,0	0,2		21,5
	Average	0,1	7,4	0,4	12,9	0,2	1,0	0,2	0,2	22,2
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,1	6,5	0,3	12,5		1,1	0		20,4
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,1	6,0	0,3	12,8		1,2	0		20,3
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0	6,2	0,3	12,2		1,2	0		19,9
	Average	0,1	6,2	0,3	12,5		1,2	0,0		20,2
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	0,1	8,9	0,4	12,3		1,8	0,1		23,6
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	0	7,7	0,4	13,8		2,4	0,1		24,4
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	0	6,8	0,4	12,5		2,2	0		22,1
	Average	0,0	7,8	0,4	12,9		2,1	0,1		23,4
47	Lobster, tail		1,2	0,7	13,9	0,5	5,5	0,3		22,1

Table 10. Monounsaturated fatty acids in seafoods. %fatty acid methyl esters.

No.	Sample	C14:1	C16:1n7	C17:1	C18:1(n9+n7+n5)	C20:1(n11+n9)	C22:1(n11+n9)	C24:1n9	Sum
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	4,3	0,2	11,9	11,5	20,7	0,7	49,4
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	4,1		10,7	13,9	23,8	0,8	53,4
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,1	3,9		10,1	13,8	26,1	0,9	54,9
	Average	0,1	4,1	0,2	10,9	13,1	23,6	0,8	52,6
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,1	9,7	0,1	12,8	13,7	15,3	0,7	52,4
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,1	10,1	0,0	12,3	12,7	14,1	0,6	50,0
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,1	10,1	0,1	12,3	13,7	15,8	0,7	52,8
	Average	0,1	10,0	0,1	12,5	13,4	15,1	0,6	51,7
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	0,1	4,0	0,3	7,2	9,5	15,1	0,9	36,9
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	0	3,9	0,3	11,2	7,6	10,8	0,8	34,5
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	0,0	3,9	0,2	10,9	9,8	15,3	0,9	41,0
	Average	0,0	3,9	0,3	9,8	8,9	13,7	0,8	37,5
47	Lobster, tail		4,7		14,8	2,2	0,4	0,2	22,3

Table 11a. Polyunsaturated fatty acids in seafoods. %fatty acid methyl esters.

No	Sample	C16:2n4	C16:3n4	C18:3n4	C18:2n6	C18:3n6	C20:3n6	C20:4n6	C22:4n6
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,4	0,5	0,9	1,2	0,1		0,3	
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,4	0,5		1,1	0,1	0,3	0,1	
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,3	0,5		1,1	0,1		0,3	
	Average	0,4	0,5	0,9	1,1	0,1	0,3	0,2	
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,4	0,5	0	1,3	0,1	0	0,3	0
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,2	0,5		1,2	0,1	0	0,3	0
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,4	0,5		1,2	0,1	0	0,3	0
	Average	0,3	0,5	0,0	1,2	0,1	0,2	0,3	0,1
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	0,4	0,4	1,9	2,1	0,1	0,1	0,3	0,1
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	0,3	0,4		1,9	0,2	0	0,2	0
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	0,3	0,4		1,6	0,2	0	0,2	0
	Average	0,3	0,4	1,9	1,8	0,2	0,1	0,2	0,2
47	Lobster, tail	0,7	3,2		0,6			2,8	

Table 11b. Polyunsaturated fatty acids in seafoods. %fatty acid methyl esters.

No.	Sample	C18:3n3	C18:4n3	C20:3n3	C20:4n3	C20:5n3 (EPA)	C22:5n3	C22:6n3 (DHA)	C20:2	C22:2	Sum
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet		2,3		0,4	6,6	0,6	10,9	0,2		24,3
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,8	2,0		0,4	5,1	0,6	8,4	0,2		19,9
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,8	1,9		0,1	4,8	0,6	8,1	0,2		18,7
	Average	0,8	2,1		0,3	5,5	0,6	9,2	0,2		22,0
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,3	1,6	0,1	0,3	9,5	0,8	8,3	0,1	0,2	23,7
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,5	1,5	0,3	0,0	10,8	0,9	9,5	0,1	0,3	26,7
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,5	1,5	0,3	0,0	9,6	0,8	8,9	0,1	0,2	25,1
	Average	0,4	1,6	0,3	0,1	9,9	0,8	8,9	0,1	0,2	25,1
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	0,2	6,7	0,4	1,0	7,1	1,0	12,9	0,3	0,5	35,3
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	1,7	6,4	0,5	1,3	7,9	1,1	14,4	0,2	0,5	37,5
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	1,4	4,9	0,3	0,9	8,0	1,2	12,7	0,2	0,1	32,8
	Average	1,1	6,0	0,4	1,1	7,7	1,1	13,3	0,2	0,4	36,4
47	Lobster, tail	0,2	0,2		0,1	17,4	1,4	16,3	5,1	5,1	53,2

3.4 Vitamins and trace elements

See Table 12.

Table 12. Analytical results for vitamin D and Iodine. Content in 100 g edible portion.

No	Sample	Vitamin D µg/100g	Iodine µg/100g
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	15,3	<20
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	14,2	<20
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	17,3	<20
	Average	15,6	
53	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked		<20
61	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Norway, cooked		<20
58	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked		<20
11	Ling, fillet		30
10	Ling, fillet		<20
66	Ling, fillet, light salted		<20

4. Provision of food information

Table 13 reports the required information for nutrient declarations. Table 14 describes the presentation of the nutrient declaration in Icelandic and table 15 in English.

Table 13. Results for nutrient declarations based on average composition. Content in 100 g edible portion.

Sample	Energy		Fat g	- of which saturates*) g	Carbo- hydrate g	- of which sugar g	Protein g	Salt g
	kJ	kcal						
Groundfish								
Deepwater redfish, fillet	428	102	3,3	0,7	0	0	18	0,21
Spotted catfish, fillet	381	91	3,4	0,6	0	0	15	0,21
Tusk, fillet	342	81	0,5	0	0	0	19	0,22
Ling, fillet	362	85	0,6	0,1	0	0	20	0,15
Witch, fillet	308	73	0,5	0,1	0	0	17	0,26
Wolf-fish, fillet	343	81	1,0	0,1	0	0	18	0,15
Megrim, fillet	349	82	0,7	0,1	0	0	19	0,31
Cod, fillet	315	74	0,7	0,1	0	0	17	0,13
Pelagic								
Blue whiting, fillet	345	81	0,6	0,1	0	0	19	0,49
Blue whiting, headed	336	79	0,8	0,1	0	0	18	0,55
Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	662	159	11	2,0	0	0	15	0,42
Capelin, whole, male fish	604	145	9,9	1,8	0	0	14	0,51
Mackerel, fillet w skin, June-Sept.	1103	266	22	4,6	0	0	17	0,26
Herring, Icelandic, fillet	713	171	11	2,2	0	0	18	0,54
Crustacean								
Lobster, tail	315	74	0,7	0,1	0	0	17	0,96
Prawn, cooked	288	68	0,9	0,1	0	0	15	1,3
Light salted products								
Ling, fillet, light salted	294	69	0,6	0,1	0	0	16	2,0
Wolf-fish, fillet, little salted	307	73	1,4	0,2	0	0	15	0,69
Pollock, fillet, light salted	268	63	0,8	0,1	0	0	14	1,2
Cod, fillet, light salted	240	57	0,5	0	0	0	13	1,6
Salted fish								
Salted fish, ling, split	458	108	0,9	0,1	0	0	25	16,0
Salted fish, pollock, split	464	110	1,5	0,2	0	0	24	22,1
Other products								
Cod skin	406	96	0,4	0	0	0	23	0,26
Cod flesh, mince	294	69	0,6	0,1	0	0	16	0,39

*) The following formula is used: Saturated fatty acids (g) = Fat (g) * fatty acid conversion factor * proportion saturated fatty acids.

The following fatty acid conversion factors were used: 0,700 for low fat fish, 0,900 for fatty fish, 0,770 for lobster and 0,800 for prawn.

Table 14. Presentation of nutrient declaration in Icelandic.

Dags.:	
Afurð:	Keila, flök
Framleiðandi:	
	Næringaryfirlýsing
Næringargildi í 100 g	
Orka	311 kJ / 73 kkal
Fita	0,24 g
- þar af mettuð fita	0 g
Kolvetni	0 g
- þar af sykurtegundir	0 g
Prótein	18 g
Salt	0,27 g
Athugasemdir:	

Efni sem eru ekki hluti af næringaryfirlýsingu

Aska	1,2 g/100g
Vatn	80,2 g/100g
Natríum	0,106 g/100g

Prófun

Summa	99,4 g/100g
-------	-------------

Table 15. Presentation of nutrient declaration.

Date:	
Product:	Tusk
Producer:	
Nutrition declaration	
Nutrient value per 100g edible product:	
Energy	311 kJ / 73 kcal
Fat	0.24 g
- of which saturates	0 g
Carbohydrate	0 g
- of which sugars	0 g
Protein	18 g
Salt	0.27 g
Comments:	

Compounds not under nutrition declaration:

Ash	1.2 g/100g
Water	80.2 g/100g
Sodium	0.106 g/100g

Test

Sum	99.4 g/100g
-----	-------------

5. References

AOAC, 1990. Phosphorus (Total) in meat. In K. Helrich (Ed.), Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists. 15th Edition. AOAC Official Method 969.31. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Arlington, USA.

AOAC, 2005. Fat (Total, saturated, and unsaturated) in foods. In K. Helrich (Ed.), Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists. AOAC Official Method 996.06. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Arlington, USA.

AOCS, 1997. Fatty acid composition by GLC. Marine oils. A.O.C.S. Official Method Ce 1b-89. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the AOCS. American Oil Chemists' Society. Champaign, Illinois, USA.

AOCS, 1997. Oil. A.O.C.S. Official Method Ba 3-38, 1997. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the AOCS. American Oil Chemists' Society. Champaign, Illinois, USA.

Bligh, E.G. and Dyer, W.S., 1959. A rapid method of total lipid extraction and purification. Can. J. Biochem. and Physiol. 37: 911

Hanson, S.W.F & Olley, J., 1963. Biochem. J. 89, 101P.

ISO, 1999. Determination of moisture and other volatile matter content. ISO Standard 6496. Geneva, Switzerland: The International Organization for Standardization.

ISO, 2002. Animal feeding stuffs – Determination of crude ash. ISO Standard 5984. Geneva, Switzerland: The International Organization for Standardization.

ISO, 2005. Determination of nitrogen content and calculation of crude protein content. ISO Standard 5983. Geneva, Switzerland: The International Organization for Standardization.

Nordisk Metodikkomité for Næringsmidler (NMKL), 2007. Trace elements – As, Cd, Hg, Pb and other elements. Determination by ICP-MS after pressure digestion. Method no. 186-2007.

Sloth, J.J., K. Julshamn, A.K. Lundebye, 2005. Total arsenic and inorganic arsenic content in Norwegian fish feed products. Aquaculture Nutrition 11: 61-66.

6. Acknowledgement

Fisheries Iceland are gratefully acknowledged for funding the project. Without this support, it would not have been possible to carry out the project.

Several people at Matis carried out the work. Ólafur Reykdal organized the project and sampling and worked on data and reports. Ragnheiður Sveinþórsdóttir worked on sampling in the Vestmannaeyjar and Gunnar Þórðarson in Ísafjörður. Svanhildur Hauksdóttir and Hafrún Hálfánardóttir worked on sample processing and proximate analysis. Natasa Desnica carried out measurements of minerals and Ingibjörg Þorvaldsdóttir carried out analysis of fatty acids. Arnljótur Bjarki Bergsson supervised finances and progress.

Appendix 1 – Information for all seafood samples

No.	Sample	Matis no.	Company code	Fresh/ frozen ^{*)}	Size grade	Sampling date	Catch month	Sample weight, g	Average weight, g
1	Deepwater redfish, fillet	R-2018-1	P	Fryst		06.07.17	03.17	7.500	
2	Deepwater redfish, fillet	R-2220-2	P	Fryst	300-500g	22.08.17	07.17	21.000	
3	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1245-2	Q	Fryst		15.05.17	04.17	13.790	1532
4	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1595-1	AR	Fersk		20.06.17	06.17	6.275	570
5	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1628-2	B	Fryst		21.06.17	04.17	50.000	1923
6	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1538-4	AA	Fryst		12.06.17	06.17	3.000	300
7	Tusk, fillet	R-439-3	Q	Fryst	500-1000g	24.01.17		9.680	968
8	Tusk, fillet	R-1245-1	Q	Fryst		15.05.17	04.17	18.560	1856
9	Tusk, fillet	R-1780-3	AH	Fryst		29.06.17	09.15	12.800	
10	Ling, fillet	R-3446-3	AD	Fryst	400-800g	22.11.16	09.16	5.830	833
11	Ling, fillet	R-1149-1	AN	Fryst		05.05.17	05.17	5.780	578
12	Ling, fillet, large	R-1628-1	B	Fryst		26.06.17	06.17	71.500	6500
13	Witch, fillet	R-572-3	AL	Fryst		31.01.17	10.16	4.110	891
14	Witch, fillet	R717-3	AF	Fryst		07.12.16	10.16	4.500	450
15	Witch, fillet	R-2324-1	AL	Fersk		29.08.17	08.17	5.600	559
16	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1140-3	AP	Fryst		30.03.17	03.17	4.816	482
17	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1245-3	Q	Fryst		15.05.17	04.17	13.850	1385
18	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-2220-1	AD	Fersk		21.08.17	08.17	5.000	500
19	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1538-1	AA	Fryst		12.06.17	06.17	1.489	149
20	Wolf-fish, fillet, small	R-3446-1	AD	Fryst	100-400g	22.11.16	10.16	5.900	227
21	Wolf-fish, fillet, large	R-3446-2	AD	Fryst	400-800g	22.11.16	10.16	5.475	391
22	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1538-3	AA	Frystir		12.06.17	06.17	1.007	101
23	Megrim, fillet	R-572-2	AL	Fryst		31.01.17		8.910	891

^{*)} Fryst: Frozen. Ferskt: Fresh

No.	Sample	Matis no.	Company code	Fresh/frozen	Size grade	Sampling date	Catch month	Sample weight, g	Average weight, g
24	Cod, fillet	R-1499-3	N	Fryst		12.06.17	06.17	7.500	750
25	Cod, fillet	R-1693-1	AS	Fersk		27.06.17	06.17	7.300	730
26	Cod, fillet	R-2497-2	N	Fersk	2000-3000	25.09.17	09.17	4.220	422
27	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1400-2	L	Fryst		22.05.17			17
28	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1452-2	L	Fryst		02.06.17	05.17	14.116	23
29	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1780-1	AH	Fryst		29.06.17	05.17	24.000	
30	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1400-1	L	Frystur		22.05.17		13.804	52
31	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1452-1	L	Frystur		02.06.17	05.17	14.116	78
32	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1780-2	AH	Frystur		29.06.17	05.17	24.000	
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1400-4	L	Fryst		22.05.17	02.16		21
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1452-3	AK	Fryst		02.06.17	02.17	13.722	19
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1499-2	AN	Fryst		08.06.17	02.17	12.600	23,9
36	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-1400-3	L	Fryst		22.05.17	02.16		27
37	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-1452-4	AK	Fryst		02.06.17	02.17	13.548	28
38	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-2292-3	P	Fryst	400+	25.08.17	02.17	26.000	62
39	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	R-2324-2	AH	Fryst	200-400g	30.08.17	08.17	25.000	275
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Agust	R-2292-2	P	Fryst		25.08.17	08.17	20.000	522
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	R-2292-1	P	Fryst		25.08.17	07.17	20.000	465
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	R-2118-1	AU	Fryst		30.06.17	06.17	17.000	380
43	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Sept.	R-2497-1	AK	Fryst		14.09.17	09.17	4.180	418
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-462-1	V	Fryst		30.01.17		3.260	163
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-572-4	AL	Fryst		31.01.17	12.16	15.286	56,7
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-572-5	AL	Fryst		31.01.17	12.16	15.375	148

No.	Sample	Matis no.	Company code	Fresh/ frozen	Size grade	Sampling date	Catch month	Sample weight, g	Average weight, g
47	Lobster, tail	R-572-1	AL	Frystir		31.01.17	7.16	790	16
48	Lobster, tail	R-717-1	AF	Frystir	24-30	07.12.16	07.16	788	16
49	Lobster, tail	R-1499-1	AN	Frystir		08.06.17	05.17	565	11,3
50	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	R-3051-1	C	Tvífryst		04.10.16	06.16	1.600	
51	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	R-1437-5	C	Tvífryst		31.05.17	05.17	447	
52	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Greenland, cooked and peeled	R-1340-2	S	Tvífryst		22.05.17			
53	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-3015-1	P	Einfryst	100 / 200	13.09.16	06.16	1.000	
54	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1340-1	S	Einfryst		22.05.17	05.17	2.572	
55	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1437-2	P	Einfryst		31.05.17	05.17	1.000	
56	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1437-4	C	Einfryst		31.05.17	05.17	403	
57	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3015-2	P	Tvífryst	200/400 200/300	15.09.16	05.16	2.000	
58	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3014-1	S	Tvífryst	300/500	19.09.16	04.16	2.500	
59	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1340-3	S	Tvífryst		22.05.17			
60	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1437-1	P	Tvífryst		31.05.17	03.17	1.000	
61	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Norway, cooked and peeled	R-3014-2	S	Tvífryst	50/150	19.09.16	08.16	2.300	
62	Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , USA, cooked and peeled	R-3014-3	S	Tvífryst	250/350	19.09.16	01.16	5.000	
63	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3015-3	P	Tvífryst	100/200	15.09.16	12.15	1.700	
64	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1437-3	P	Tvífryst		31.05.17	12.16	1.167	
65	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-2266-1	C	Tvífryst		22.08.17	12.16	2.500	

No.	Sample	Matis no.	Company code	Fresh/ frozen	Size grade	Sampling date	Catch month	Sample weight, g	Average weight, g
66	Ling, fillet, light salted	R-439-2	Q	Fryst		24.01.17		7.267	726
67	Pollock, pieces, light salted	R-1143-2	H	Lausfryst		04.04.17	04.17	6.632	663
68	Cod, pieces, light salted	R717-2	AF	Frystir		07.12.16		5.114	269
69	Cod, pieces, light salted	R-1149-2	AQ	Frystir		05.05.17	03.17	4.080	
70	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-173-1	AA	Lausfryst	500-1000g	17.11.16	11.16		
71	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-173-2	AL	Lausfryst		13.12.16		11.450	1145
72	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-1140-2	AP	Fryst		30.03.17	03.17	3.860	473
73	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-1143-1	H	Lausfryst		05.04.17	03.17	8.340	834
74	Cod, fillet, light salted, small	R-972-2	AD	Fryst	200-500	27.03.17	09.16	3.558	356
75	Cod, fillet, light salted, large	R-972-1	AD	Fryst	500-1000	27.03.17	09.16	5.814	581
76	Cod, loin, light salted	R-439-1	Q	Frystir		24.01.17		4.262	328
77	Cod, loin, light salted	R-1140-1	AP	Lausfryst		30.03.17	03.17	5.012	501
78	Salted fish, ling, split	R-572-6	AL			31.01.17		14.000	1.400
79	Salted fish, pollock, split	R-628-1	AL			13.12.16			
80	Cod skin	R-1499-4	N	Ferskt		12.06.17	06.17	1.330	133
81	Cod skin	R-1693-2	AS	Ferskt		27.06.17	06.17	1.416	
82	Cod skin	R-1823-1	AT	Ferskt		11.07.17	07.17	1.200	50
83	Cod flesh, mince	R-1141-1	Q	Frystur		07.04.17		7.864	
84	Cod flesh, mince	R-2266-2	V	Frystur		07.07.17	07.17	7.000	
85	Cod flesh, mince	R-2018-2	P	Frystur		06.07.17		7.500	

Appendix 2 – Results for proximates in all seafood samples. Content per 100 g edible portion.

No	Sample	Matis no.	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
1	Deepwater redfish, fillet	R-2018-1	16,9	4,20	1,2	78,2	100,5
2	Deepwater redfish, fillet	R-2220-2	18,2	2,41	1,1	79,0	100,7
3	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1245-2	15,4	1,97	1,1	83,4	101,9
4	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1595-1	13,7	2,39	1,0	83,5	100,6
5	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1628-2	14,7	4,72	0,9	80,8	101,1
6	Spotted catfish, fillet	R-1538-4	16,2	4,66	0,9	78,4	100,2
7	Tusk, fillet	R-439-3	18,9	0,56	1,2	80,3	101,0
8	Tusk, fillet	R-1245-1	19,6	0,57	1,1	79,8	101,1
9	Tusk, fillet	R-1780-3	17,8	0,24	1,2	80,2	99,4
10	Ling, fillet	R-3446-3	18,3	0,10	1,0	78,6	98,0
11	Ling, fillet	R-1149-1	20,7	0,56	1,2	78,9	101,4
12	Ling, fillet, large	R-1628-1	19,8	0,58	1,1	79,6	101,1
13	Witch, fillet	R-572-3	17,0	0,49	1,2	81,2	99,9
14	Witch, fillet	R717-3	17,2	0,57	1,1	82,0	100,9
15	Witch, fillet	R-2324-1	17,0	0,56	1,1	82,1	100,8
16	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1140-3	14,6	1,39	1,3	83,5	100,8
17	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1245-3	15,8	1,33	1,2	82,8	101,1
18	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-2220-1	16,8	0,94	1,2	81,7	100,6
19	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1538-1	18,5	0,44	1,1	80,3	100,3
20	Wolf-fish, fillet, small	R-3446-1	20,1	0,70	1,1	79,7	101,6
21	Wolf-fish, fillet, large	R-3446-2	18,5	1,80	1,1	78,4	99,8
22	Wolf-fish, fillet	R-1538-3	18,7	0,81	1,2	80,4	101,1
23	Megrim, fillet	R-572-2	18,8	0,68	1,2	79,6	100,3

No	Sample	Matis no.	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
24	Cod, fillet	R-1499-3	17,1	0,56	1,1	82,5	101,3
25	Cod, fillet	R-1693-1	17,1	0,60	1,2	82,0	100,9
26	Cod, fillet	R-2497-2	17,5	0,78	1,2	81,5	101,0
27	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1400-2	18,3	0,65	1,6	80,5	101,1
28	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1452-2	19,3	0,70	2,0	79,6	101,6
29	Blue whiting, fillet	R-1780-1	19,4	0,43	1,4	78,8	100,0
30	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1400-1	18,1	0,92	2,6	78,6	100,2
31	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1452-1	18,3	0,98	2,5	78,5	100,3
32	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	R-1780-2	18,4	0,53	1,8	78,7	99,4
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1400-4	14,8	11,68	1,8	70,0	98,3
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1452-3	15,0	10,80	1,9	72,3	100,0
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	R-1499-2	14,2	10,80	1,9	72,5	99,4
36	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-1400-3	14,1	9,29	1,7	74,2	99,3
37	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-1452-4	14,5	10,49	2,3	73,0	100,3
38	Capelin, whole, male fish	R-2292-3	13,8	9,80	2,1	73,7	99,4
39	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	R-2324-2	17,2	22,63	1,2	56,9	97,9
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Agust	R-2292-2	16,2	26,05	1,1	54,4	97,8
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	R-2292-1	17,2	19,63	1,3	58,7	96,8
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	R-2118-1	17,8	18,10	1,3	63,4	100,6
43	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Sept.	R-2497-1	15,8	25,40	1,1	54,8	97,1
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-462-1	18,2	11,70	1,6	68,2	99,7
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-572-4	17,8	9,54	1,6	70,3	99,2
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	R-572-5	17,2	10,7	1,5	70,3	99,7

No	Sample	Matis no.	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
47	Lobster, tail	R-572-1	16,0	0,60	2,0	81,7	100,3
48	Lobster, tail	R-717-1	17,3	0,84	1,9	80,4	100,4
49	Lobster, tail	R-1499-1	16,1	0,64	2,1	80,6	99,4
50	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	R-3051-1	16,1	0,10	2,0	82,0	100,2
51	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	R-1437-5	14,4	0,93	1,8	83,0	100,1
52	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Greenland, cooked and peeled	R-1340-2	15,1	0,90	2,2	82,4	100,6
53	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-3015-1	16,5	0,60	1,8	81,0	99,9
54	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1340-1	15,9	1,26	2,1	81,9	101,2
55	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1437-2	13,8	0,81	2,5	83,7	100,8
56	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	R-1437-4	18,7	1,28	1,9	79,6	101,5
57	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3015-2	14,6	0,30	2,0	83,1	100,0
58	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3014-1	13,9	0,40	1,9	84,0	100,2
59	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1340-3	15,0	1,03	2,0	82,7	100,7
60	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1437-1	15,2	0,88	2,1	82,6	100,8
61	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Norway, cooked and peeled	R-3014-2	14,9	0,20	2,1	82,3	99,5
62	Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , USA, cooked and peeled	R-3014-3	12,4	0,40	2,1	84,5	99,4
63	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-3015-3	15,4	0,10	1,7	81,9	99,1
64	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-1437-3	16,5	1,10	2,2	81,3	101,1
65	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	R-2266-1	14,3	0,96	1,8	83,2	100,3

No	Sample	Matis no.	Protein g	Fat g	Ash g	Water g	Sum g
66	Ling, fillet, light salted	R-439-2	15,7	0,55	2,7	82,2	101,2
67	Pollock, pieces, light salted	R-1143-2	13,7	0,84	2,1	83,8	100,4
68	Cod, pices, light salted	R717-2	12,1	0,53	2,8	84,8	100,2
69	Cod, pieces, light salted	R-1149-2	16,6	0,56	2,9	81,1	101,2
70	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-173-1	13,2	0,43	2,0	85,0	100,6
71	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-173-2	13,1	0,42	3,3	84,0	100,8
72	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-1140-2	12,5	0,61	2,6	84,7	100,4
73	Cod, fillet, light salted	R-1143-1	13,7	0,65	2,1	84,7	101,2
74	Cod, fillet, light salted, small	R-972-2	11,9	0,28	2,4	85,6	100,2
75	Cod, fillet, light salted, large	R-972-1	12,0	0,44	2,5	85,4	100,3
76	Cod, loin, light salted	R-439-1	13,4	0,58	2,5	84,1	100,6
77	Cod, loin, light salted	R-1140-1	13,2	0,61	2,2	84,5	100,5
78	Salted fish, ling, split	R-572-6	25,2	0,90	20,0	60,9	107,0
79	Salted fish, pollock, split	R-628-1	24,2	1,54	19,1	55,8	100,6
80	Cod skin	R-1499-4	26,0	0,30	2,7	74,1	103,1
81	Cod skin	R-1693-2	25,2	0,40	3,2	73,1	101,9
82	Cod skin	R-1823-1	25,7	0,52	2,6	74,4	103,2
83	Cod flesh, mince	R-1141-1	14,7	0,76	1,3	84,2	101,0
84	Cod flesh, mince	R-2266-2	16,7	0,64	1,0	81,9	100,2
85	Cod flesh, mince	R-2018-2	16,4	0,40	1,1	81,6	99,5

Appendix 3 – Results for minerals in all seafood samples. Content per 100 g edible portion.

No.	Sample	Salt	Sodium	Magnesium	Phosphorus	Potassium	Calcium	Total phosphates
		g	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg
1	Deepwater redfish, fillet	0,25	98	36	180	319	33	
2	Deepwater redfish, fillet	0,17	69	32	163	280	23	
3	Spotted catfish, fillet	0,23	91	20	176	346	9	
4	Spotted catfish, fillet	0,27	108	24	252	417	9	
5	Spotted catfish, fillet	0,20	79	17	174	289	8	
6	Spotted catfish, fillet	0,15	59	13	144	199	3	
7	Tusk, fillet	0,23	92	22	101	119	10	
8	Tusk, fillet	0,16	65	22	144	310	16	
9	Tusk, fillet	0,27	106	22	157	269	17	
10	Ling, fillet	0,13	52	22	146	261	20	
11	Ling, fillet	0,15	59	23	166	332	7	
12	Ling, fillet, large	0,18	70	22	162	296	7	
13	Witch, fillet	0,26	104	23	96	124	6	
14	Witch, fillet	0,28	112	22	131	231	44	
15	Witch, fillet	0,24	94	22	145	312	15	
16	Wolf-fish, fillet	0,69	274	13	111	158	5	292
17	Wolf-fish, fillet	0,20	81	19	190	384	11	
18	Wolf-fish, fillet	0,16	62	30	201	351	11	
19	Wolf-fish, fillet	0,14	55	18	171	286	8	
20	Wolf-fish, fillet, small	0,12	49	20	164	280	17	
21	Wolf-fish, fillet, large	0,12	48	18	163	268	12	
22	Wolf-fish, fillet	0,13	53	19	176	306	5	
23	Megrim, fillet	0,31	124	30	117	140	11	

No.	Sample	Salt	Sodium	Magnesium	Phosphorus	Potassium	Calcium	Total phosphates
		g	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg
24	Cod, fillet	0,13	50	20	170	310	4	461
25	Cod, fillet	0,13	51	19	172	298	4	472
26	Cod, fillet	0,14	56	20	187	421	12	496
27	Blue whiting, fillet	0,47	187	35	201	291	49	
28	Blue whiting, fillet	0,70	280	53	190	369	56	
29	Blue whiting, fillet	0,31	123	28	165	274	13	
30	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	0,57	226	43	328	290	243	
31	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	0,76	302	59	375	316	441	
32	Blue whiting, headed, gutted	0,34	137	31	183	270	47	
33	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,41	162	29	359	217	195	
34	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,44	177	32	237	235	132	
35	Capelin, whole, spawn with roe	0,41	163	27	286	240	191	
36	Capelin, whole, male fish	0,38	153	28	376	242	312	
37	Capelin, whole, male fish	0,62	246	41	298	241	291	
38	Capelin, whole, male fish	0,53	212	44	279	249	221	
39	Mackerel, fillet w skin, August	0,16	62	24	210	336	5	
40	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Agust	0,27	108	29	189	302	10	
41	Mackerel, fillet w skin, July	0,35	139	55	220	336	18	
42	Mackerel, fillet w skin, June	0,32	128	47	215	324	<5	
43	Mackerel, fillet w skin, Sept.	0,22	87	23	206	410	44	
44	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,49	195	40	158	153	16	510
45	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,59	237	46	235	281	38	488
46	Herring, Icelandic, fillet	0,55	219	47	257	268	60	475

No.	Sample	Salt	Sodium	Magnesium	Phosphorus	Potassium	Calcium	Total phosphates
		g	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg
47	Lobster, tail	0,99	396	48	142	68	43	
48	Lobster, tail	0,98	391	52	190	249	75	
49	Lobster, tail	0,90	360	58	191	181	107	
50	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	1,21	485	13	75	56	27	216
51	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Barents Sea, cooked and peeled	1,45	579	18	76	51	60	146
52	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Greenland, cooked and peeled	1,49	595	22	116	43	47	207
53	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	1,01	405	23	116	75	37	339
54	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	1,35	541	25	148	46	47	346
55	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	1,64	657	24	92	54	77	151
56	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Iceland, cooked and peeled	1,06	425	40	143	121	61	351
57	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,00	398	13	56	42	38	208
58	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,24	497	12	59	23	24	195
59	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,29	517	18	100	32	29	202
60	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,71	682	23	107	93	41	197
61	Prawn, <i>P. borealis</i> , Norway, cooked and peeled	1,05	421	11	63	29	22	225
62	Prawn, <i>P. jodani</i> , USA, cooked and peeled	1,04	417	15	75	20	44	259
63	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,13	450	16	78	50	27	193
64	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,44	575	30	146	109	40	333
65	Prawn, <i>P. montegui</i> , Canada, cooked and peeled	1,30	520	25	79	40	41	

No.	Sample	Salt	Sodium	Magnesium	Phosphorus	Potassium	Calcium	Total phosphates
		g	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg	mg
66	Ling, fillet, light salted	1,98	790	17	75	63	8	223
67	Pollock, pieces, light salted	1,24	494	18	128	218	12	314
68	Cod, pieces, light salted	2,12	848	12	80	89	9	
69	Cod, pieces, light salted	1,76	702	48	137	235	25	334
70	Cod, fillet, light salted	1,31	523	14	117	132	3	232
71	Cod, fillet, light salted	2,20	880	12	127	173	173	260
72	Cod, fillet, light salted	1,80	718	14	96	138	12	248
73	Cod, fillet, light salted	1,38	550	16	103	179	11	265
74	Cod, fillet, light salted, small	1,41	565	10	151	220	10	403
75	Cod, fillet, light salted, large	1,38	550	12	187	262	65	484
76	Cod, loin, light salted	1,49	596	13	60	52	2	219
77	Cod, loin, light salted	1,22	487	14	107	185	7	302
78	Salted fish, ling, split	16,00	6401	29	135	200	42	299
79	Salted fish, pollock, split	22,08	8833	47	240	332	43	404
80	Cod skin	0,19	74	7	135	102	96	
81	Cod skin	0,51	202	18	477	63	726	
82	Cod skin	0,10	38	34	417	179	528	
83	Cod flesh, mince	0,66	264	13	92	151	8	
84	Cod flesh, mince	0,19	77	28	150	256	9	
85	Cod flesh, mince	0,32	129	34	174	307	8	

Appendix 4 – A sampling template

Verkefnið Næringargildi sjávarafurða – merkingar og svörun

Sýnatökueyðublað

Sýni þurfa að vera dæmigerð fyrir framleiðslu fyrirtækisins.

Dagsetning sýnatöku: _____

Fyrirtæki: _____

Sýni (fisktegund, flök/bitar, m roði/roðlaust, frosið / ekki frosið): _____

Magn sýnis (10 flök bolfiskur / 40 flök síld / 50 humarhalar): _____

Uppruni sýnis eins og þekkt er (veiðislóð): _____

Tímasetning veiða: _____

Vinnsluaðferð: _____

Stærðarflokkur: _____

Umsjón sýnatöku / tengiliður hjá fyrirtæki: _____

Appendix 5 – A registration template for sample information

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Sýni:	Langa flök, fryst			Sýnataka, dags.:		22.11.2016		
Fyrirtæki	Oddi hf			Sýnavinnsla, dags.:		9.12.2016		
Lýsing sýnis:				Sýnisnúmer:		F160-3446-3		
<p>Gerð sýnis (frosið / ekki frosið, flök / bitar, roð / roðlaust): Frosið, roðlaust</p> <p>Stærðarflokkur: 400-800g Best fyrir merking: 23.09.2018 Magn og aðrar merkingar á umbúðum:</p>								
Uppruni: Veiðisvæði, sýnataka, tími.								
Uppruni: Framleiðsludagur: Veiðisvæði: Löndun:								
Sýnavinnsla:								
Mælingar á þyngd					Athugasemdir:			
Þyngd sýnis (fyrir uppþiðingu)			5830	g	7 flök			
Þyngd roðs ef við á				g				
Þyngd beina og afskurðar				g				
Þyngd vatns (hrips):			511	g				
Drip + íshúð			8,8	%				
Fjöldi Flaka			7	flök				
Meðalþyngd flaka			833	g				